

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND FORMATION OF HR SYSTEM IN THE CONDITIONS OF DEVELOPING THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN NETWORKS

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Abstract: This article covers the use of digital economy in the fields of strategic management of industrial enterprises and HR system formation. Also, the organizational-economic mechanism of strategic management of industrial enterprises and the formation of HR system in the innovative management system was analyzed, its specific features and existing problems were identified.

Key words: innovation, efficiency, innovative management, scientific research, experimental construction developments.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the processes of transformation of the post-industrial economy into a form based on the systematic use of ICT or known as "digital economy" have been accelerating. The digital economy is becoming a logical continuation of the evolutionary development of the digital ecosystem for a particular country and an opportunity to form an innovative economy that fully covers the state, enterprises, and the population.

Implementation of a single information base for the calculation of production indicators in the real sector of the economy, optimization of the existing information system for automation of production and management processes, and improvement of the CRM system, introduction of an information system for project management and evaluation of the KPI level of employees, "Roadmap" for 2022-2023 has been developed for the implementation of a unified system of personnel management (HR) for fully functional monitoring of the stages of work with employees.¹

The priorities of the reforms implemented in our country today are to accelerate the introduction of innovative projects in various sectors of the national economy, including the production of innovative products by industrial enterprises, the achievement of high economic growth indicators due to the wide use of management innovations in practice, as well as 0 It is aimed at further increasing the indicators of Uzbekistan in the global rankings. In particular, the government of our country has set a long-term strategic goal to

¹ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for wide implementation of digital economy and electronic government" No. PQ-4699 dated 04/28/2020.

become one of the top 50 countries in the world by 2030 in the Global Innovation Index.²

METHODS

In the process of writing a scientific article, systematic analysis, historicity and logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative and selective research, monographic analysis and grouping methods of scientific research were used.

RESULTS

Based on the analysis of the indicators of innovative efficiency of industrial enterprises, it is possible to assess the extent to which the innovative activity of the enterprise is organized, as well as its existing achievements and shortcomings. In the conditions of a perfectly competitive market economy, further improvement of the existing management system is achieved based on the evaluation of the indicators of the innovative efficiency of the management of industrial enterprises. Transferring the economic activity of the enterprise to the path of innovative development is achieved by introducing a modern management system in its management practice, as well as technical and technological modernization of production, implementation of innovative projects in production processes. Based on the assessment of the efficiency of innovative management in the enterprise, it will be possible to determine the indicators of economic efficiency achieved due to the introduction of innovative projects into production. This situation serves to a certain extent in the practice of enterprise management, as well as for the improvement of its competitive indicators in the market.³

According to the analysis of the results of the survey conducted by the World Bank, the indicator of innovative activity of industrial enterprises in our country is significantly lower than in other developing and developing market economies. In particular, despite the fact that the share of enterprises that spent on financing the scientific research and experimental design development of the industrial enterprises of our country is high compared to the average indicators of low-middle income countries, Central Asia and European countries, the amount of expenses spent on this is significantly less compared to other countries.

² Decree No. PF5544 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021", 21.09.2018.

³ Bakhtiyorov Bobur Bahodir o'g'li, "Scientific-methodical basis of evaluating the effectiveness of innovative management of industrial enterprises / Real sector of the economy / Real sector economy 2021. p. 115"

Figure 1. In 2018-2022, indicators of the innovative activity of industrial enterprises in developing and developing countries, in percentage ⁴

Also, the percentage of enterprises implementing product and management innovations in our country is low compared to other countries (see Figure 1). This situation has a negative impact on the global competitiveness of the products produced by the industrial enterprises of our country in the world market.

According to the experts of the World Bank, the indicator of economic efficiency of the enterprises that implemented the innovative project compared to the enterprises with traditional management practices depends on factors such as the characteristics of a certain economic region or industry, the scale of the enterprise (large, medium or small). Despite the decrease or increase of secret circles, it is high in the range of 20-45 percent.

According to the results of the analysis of the ownership form of industrial enterprises in the implementation of innovative management practices in our country, state enterprises and foreign firms take the leading place compared to private enterprises. The analysis shows that private enterprises, especially small and medium-sized enterprises, have high requirements for financing innovations, including the use of services of financial service organizations for their financing, as well as the qualifications of employees in enterprises. the presence of problems such as insufficiency has been determined.

CONCLUSION

⁴ Internet portal SNG. <https://e-cis.info/news/566/96517/#gallery-2..>

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Through the establishment of associations of industrial enterprises engaged in innovative activities in the regions, besides increasing the speed of mutual transfer of innovations, it allows further development of innovative cooperation relations between enterprises. Based on the proposed mechanism, associations of regional industrial enterprises will have to perform the following tasks:

- implementation of innovative projects by industrial enterprises;
- formation of cooperation between industrial enterprises on the implementation of innovative projects;
- acceleration of mutual transfer of innovations between industrial enterprises;
- conducting innovative marketing research;
- formation of requirements for new innovative projects;
- to improve the efficiency of using internal and external opportunities in the development of innovative activities of industrial enterprises.

In our opinion, in the following years, by forming reports on innovative management based on the methodology proposed by industrial enterprises in our country, not only enterprises, but also to evaluate the level of innovative development of our country's economy, as well as to develop state programs aimed at identifying existing shortcomings and eliminating them. This creates a basis for the successful implementation of the innovative development strategy in our country in the long term.

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